

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASÍDA ARALÍQTAN OQÍTÍWDÍN INTEGRACIYASÍ»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

EFFECTIVE USE OF FAIRY TALES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPOKEN AND WRITTEN LANGUAGE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS

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Abstract: *In this article, the effective use of fairy tales in the development of oral and written speech of primary school pupils. Teaching harmonizes images with the animal world. The effect on the further expansion of the vocabulary chorus is noted. There is talk about developing the scope of world knowledge more creatively.*

Keywords: *oral speech, written speech, fairy tales, multimedia technologies.*

The fact that pupils know how to speak their own language means that their speech is still developed. By introducing them to the facts of the language, by teaching them to be able to stay in their lives, or by teaching them the truth of life, we influence the development of their action. The development of this thought-meadow leads to the elevation of their speech. Therefore, language facts should be taught more to the pupils of the class.

When a pupil comes to school, he has a certain level of speaking experience and comes with his own vocabulary. It is formed due to the fact that they are participles with exercises. Now, with coming to school, the conditions of participation in the team will change. Different types of participation and the use of previously unknown terms appeared, so the task of developing his speech was set from the day he arrived at school [1:18].

Pupils who have started school have from one and a half thousand to three thousand words. Now, being a pupil, he did not use the word empty like before. The atmosphere changes it. The pupil will now be under the supervision of his teacher and companions. For this reason, his speech begins with a certain pattern. The pupil will not get used to this situation quickly. Therefore, the teacher remembers such a characteristic of the pupil and organizes work. It guides them to get feedback, answer questions, learn by speaking, and communicate with their companions. The same requirement is placed on their written language as well. Of course, in the early period, the written language develops more slowly than the spoken language. Consequently, a different requirement is imposed from the written language.

Teaching fairy tales in primary grades places the following demands on teachers:

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1. To create good reading qualities in pupils based on the texts of fairy tales;
2. To achieve full understanding of the content of the text by pupils;
3. To teach to distinguish between characters in fairy tales;
4. Teaching pupils to correctly understand events, life facts, fantasy;
5. Achieving aesthetic pleasure of pupils;
6. Ensuring correct understanding of difficult words in fairy tales;
7. To reach certain conclusions by comparing their own moral qualities with the moral qualities of characters;
8. To get the pupils to tell the stories completely in the second person.

The fairy tale “Strength in unity” given in the lesson “Native language and reading literacy” intended for the 1st grade told the pupils that the result of joint work will be productive and high, and that everything can be done together. Fairy tales are very important in the development of pupils’ language. After reading a fairy tale, a pupil can clearly and comprehensibly describe and narrate the concepts of his solitary thoughts. An addition to this story tells from his point of view. Also, in the story “Why does the cat eat and drink and bathe?” given in this textbook, based on the story of the cat and the pig, the fact that all cats eat and bathe becomes a reflex of pupils. A pupil can also know well what an animal is like, what it feeds on, where it lives, and the shores of a pupil’s fairy tale. The teacher can learn the meaning of this fairy tale in the ratio of a pupil to a person close to him. After reading the story, you can ask the following questions:

1. What did bird say to the cat?
2. What do you know about cats?
3. Do you have a cat at home?

The purpose of making such requests is to strengthen the pupil’s knowledge, to further develop language skills, and to teach animals to live together in friendship [2:73]

The fairy tale “The Attack of the Deer” given in the textbook “Native Language and Reading Literacy” intended for the 2nd grade tells about the story of an old man and a herd of deer. In the fairy tale, deer are hungry and come to houses in the village in search of food, and the owner of the house tries to shoot them with a pistol while they are hunting. The conclusion of this fairy tale is that it encourages people to be kind to animals and condemns hunting. To further discuss this story, we ask readers the following questions:

1. Why did the herd of deer enter the house?

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2. Why was the owner surprised?

3. How did the deer greet the deer who owned the house? [3:38].

The purpose of the fairy tales given in such textbooks greatly helps the pupil to know the cognitive world around him, to learn it, to clearly understand his place and direction there. Therefore, fairy tales play an important role in the development of a pupil's oral and communicative speech. They can freely express their thoughts to another person about what they have learned and seen in the development of the pupil's oral language. As much as the pupil tells about what he has seen, learned and learned orally, in the future, when he writes narrative and artistic works, his thoughts and suggestions will be easily and completely put down on paper. Then he becomes a free, educated person.

It is our main goal to teach pupils to be able to adjust and develop civilized speech skills, to express their thoughts and feelings orally or in writing, to communicate with others. To develop students' oral and written speech, to say words correctly, to enrich vocabulary, to master words, to be able to stay in place, previously learned and new place it is necessary to make sentences from learned words, to form a speech. The pupil should have enough vocabulary to make his thoughts and inner feelings understandable to the listener, and he should have sufficient knowledge of the grammar rules of the Karakalpak language, the culture of speech, and the knowledge he received in the speech class.

In order to form pupils' speaking skill, we need to rely on new pedagogical technologies, find effective methods of work, optimal methods of organizing work with pupils, and conduct in-depth research to determine the content of education. This, in turn, shows the development of pupils' consciousness, the ways of using various methods in teaching the tasks and tasks of education, the development of pupils' spirituality, the stages of their thoughts and actions.

It is necessary to determine and continuously study the issues of stage formation, development of ideas-meadows in the course of education, generalization of the theoretical foundations of problem-based teaching, and the close connection of speaking actions with other actions. We don't just tell fairy tales to pupils, we develop their imaginations by illuminating them with actions and evaluating the actions of each character.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the development of pupils' oral, written and connected speech in the classes of the natively language, if fairy tales are decorated with different types of stories, new innovative technologies, multimedia and slide films,

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the students will fully accept the subject. Teachers will achieve their goals if pupils' understanding of a new topic is comprehensively formed. By developing the concepts of seeing fairy-tale heroes based on people's lifestyles, pupils will have the ability to distinguish between real life and fairy-tale life.

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